

curriculum vitae with lists of publications of **TÖTÖSY de ZEPETNEK, Steven**
Genève: Zenodo, 2026- <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18842375>>

version 2026.06.26.

previous versions: 2000-2026 <<https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/totosycv>> in
CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture. West Lafayette: Purdue University Press.

Academic appointments: Sichuan University (Yangtze River Scholar & Professor 2024-2029), National Sun Yat-sen University (Professor 2008-2010), University of Halle-Wittenberg (Prof.Dr. 2002-2011), University of Alberta (Assistant Professor 1989-2000, Lecturer 1984-1989) & (Distinguished) Visiting Professor at universities in Asia, Europe, India, USA 1989-

Editorial appointments: Routledge Press (Co-editor of learned journal 2018-), Purdue University Press (Editor of learned journal 1999-2016 & book series 2001-2016), Shaker Press (Editor of book series 2006-2013), Canadian Comparative Literature Association / Association Canadienne de Littérature Comparée (Associate Editor 1992-1997 & Assistant Editor 1989-1992), University of Alberta (Editor of book series 1989-2000), Carleton University (Editorial Assistant 1981-1982)
contact: <totosysteven@mac.com>

1) bioprofile 2) fields of scholarship & teaching 3) academic appointments & service 4) publications 5) publications about Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek's work 6) funding for research & publishing scholarship 7) conference organization & participation

1) bioprofile: Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek's <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18842375>> research, teaching, and publications are in comparative literature, comparative cultural studies, and media and communication studies including postcolonial studies, (im)migration & ethnic minority studies, feminist & gender studies, film & literature, digital humanities, readership & audience studies, Holocaust studies, online course design in the humanities, editing & publishing in print & digital, and history (genealogy and heraldry). Education: Ph.D. 1989 Comparative Literature University of Alberta; B.Ed. 1984 History and English as a Second Language University of Ottawa; M.A. 1983 Comparative Literature Carleton University; B.A. 1980 History and German Studies The University of Western Ontario; high school in Germany, Austria, Switzerland (diploma) 1965-1974. Languages: English, French, German, Hungarian & reading Latin, Italian, Spanish, Russian. University appointments include Lecturer, Assistant Professor, Professor, Editor of learned journals and book series: University of Alberta, Purdue University, University of Halle-Wittenberg, Northeastern University, National Sun Yat-sen University, Sichuan University, and (Distinguished) Visiting Professor at universities in Asia, Europe, India, USA. Publications: 6 single-authored books; 281 articles, bibliographies, book reviews, research resources including 35 edited volumes & guest-edited issues of learned journals. Tötösy de Zepetnek's work is also published in translation to Chinese, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Macedonian, Mahrati, Polish, Portuguese, and Spanish.

2) fields of scholarship & teaching: comparative literature (theory & Canadian-, English-, French-, German-, Hungarian-language literatures and cultures), comparative cultural studies (theory & literature and culture as system[s]), the sociology of cultural production & participation, comparative media and intermediality studies, digital humanities, print & digital publishing of scholarship, online course design & teaching, readership & audience studies, cultural policy, humanities & pedagogy, communication studies (intercultural communication & conflict mediation), the study of rhetoric, discourse studies, translation studies, English as a Second Language, diaspora & ethnic minority & (im)migration literatures & cultures, comparative Central & East European studies, Holocaust studies, the modern novel, themes & motifs in comparative world literatures, film & literature, postcolonial studies, women's writing (feminist & gender theory & criticism), history, history (genealogy, heraldry, bibliography)

3) academic appointments & service

3.1 academic appointments / 3.2 academic service

3.1 academic appointments

Sichuan University: 长江学者 (Yangtze River Scholar) & Professor Department of Comparative Literature and World Literature 2024-2029 <<https://lj.scu.edu.cn/info/1105/7113.htm>>

Sichuan University: Visiting Professor Department of Comparative Literature and World Literature 2013, 2014, 2015, 2020-2022

Sichuan University: Member Advisory Board Mutual Learning among Civilizations: China and the World 2024-

Routledge Press & Sichuan University: Co-editor *Comparative Literature: East & West / 比较文学: 东方与西方* 2018-

Purdue University & Purdue University Press: Editor (Founding 1998) *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* <<https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweb/>> 2000-2016 & Series Editor Books in Comparative Cultural Studies 2001-2016 & Visiting Professor 2012-2016

National Sun Yat-sen University: Professor Department of Foreign Languages and Literature & Center for the Humanities and Social Sciences 2008-2010 & Distinguished Visiting Professor Faculty of Humanities 2006

Central China Normal University: Visiting Professor Faculty of Humanities 2015

Tsinghua University: Distinguished Visiting Professor Faculty of Humanities 2013

Ghent University: Visiting Professor Faculty of Education 2011-2013

University of Hyderabad: Distinguished Visiting Professor Faculty of Humanities 2010

University of Liverpool: Research Fellow Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences 2010

Kuwait University: Distinguished Visiting Professor Faculty of Humanities 2010

Complutense University Madrid: Distinguished Visiting Professor Faculty of Philology 2007-2008

Northeastern University: Associate Professor 2007-2008, Lecturer 2000-2001 Department of Communication Studies

Series Editor "Books in Comparative Culture, Media, and Communication Studies" Aachen: Shaker Press 2006-2013

University of Santiago de Compostela: Distinguished Visiting Professor Faculty of Humanities 2006

University of Halle-Wittenberg: Prof.Dr. Department of Media and Communication Studies 2002-2011

University of Leipzig: Visiting Professor Centre for the History and Culture of East-Central Europe 1998

Peking University: Visiting Professor Faculty of Humanities 1994, 1995, 1996

József Attila University: Visiting Professor Faculty of Humanities 1995

University of Alberta: Associate Director 1992-2000, Assistant Director 1989-1992, Assistant Professor 1992-2000 Research Institute for Comparative Literature; Lecturer 1984-1989 Department of Comparative Literature, Department of English, Department of German Studies, Faculty of Extension; Editor (founding) *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* 1998-2000;

Associate Editor 1992-1997 & Assistant Editor 1989-1992 *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée*; Series Editor "Books in Comparative Literature" 1989-2000

Guest Editor *Comparative Literature* 2015; *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* 2000, 2009, 2011, 2013; *Reader: Essays in Reader-Oriented Theory, Criticism, and Pedagogy* 1996; *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée* 1995, 1996

Carleton University: Editorial Assistant *Les Littératures de langues européennes au tournant du siècle*. Carleton University 1981-

1982

3.2 academic service

Member Research Committee DCL: Digital Comparative Literature, ICLA/AILC: International Comparative Literature Association

Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée 2024-

Member International Advisory Board 外国语文论丛 (Collected Essays of Foreign Languages and Literatures): 2022-

Member International Advisory Board *Yearbook of Hungarian Studies* (Babes-Bolyai University & De Gruyter Sciendo) 2020-

Member International Advisory Board *Metacritic Journal for Comparative Studies and Theory* (Babes-Bolyai University) 2017-

Elected Member Academia Scientiarum et Artium Europaea / European Academy of Sciences and Arts 2015-

Member International Association of Hungarian Professors (Magyar Professzorok Nemzetközi Szövetsége) 2012-

Member International Advisory Board *Cultura: International Journal of Philosophy of Culture and Axiology* (Alexandru Ioan Cuza University) 2012-2024
 Member External Advisory Board *Journal of Artistic Creation and Literary Research / Revista de creación e investigación literaria* (Complutense University Madrid) 2012-
 Member International Advisory Board *1616: Anuario de la Sociedad Española de Literatura General y Comparada* 2010-
 Correspondent *CKCU Literary News: Literatures in Europe Today* Carleton University Radio CKCU-FM 2010-
 Member International Advisory Board *Revista Ixchel* (Asociación de Literatura Comparada en América Central y el Caribe) 2009-
 Member Council International Institute of Business and Social Communication 2009-
 Member Advisory Board *452°F: Revista de Teoría de la Literatura y Literatura Comparada / Journal of Literary Theory and Comparative Literature* (University Autónoma Barcelona) 2009-2012
 Member Executive Board Réseau Européen d'Etudes Littéraires Comparées / European Network for Comparative Literary Studies 2009-2011
 Member Program Committee American Comparative Literature Association 2009-2010
 Member Editorial Board *Journal of International and Intercultural Communication* (Taylor & Francis) 2008-
 Member International Advisory Board Center for the Humanities and Social Sciences, National Sun Yat-sen University 2008-2016
 Member Advisory Board *extravío: revista electrónica de literatura comparada* (University of València) 2006-2015
 Member Committee E-Journals Council of Editors of Learned Journals (USA) 2006-2008
 Vice-chair Research Committee on Comparative Literature in the Digital Age, ICLA/AILC: International Comparative Literature Association / Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée 2006-2007
 Member Society of Hungarian Authors (Magyar Szépirok Társasága) 2006-
 Corporate Member Scientists Abroad Hungarian Academy of Sciences / MTA: Magyar Tudományos Akadémia Köztisztviselői Külső Tag 2003- List of publications <<https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10103807>> (MTA ID 10026087 & MTMT database ID 10103807)
 Member Halle Institute of Media / Hallesches Institut für Medien University of Halle-Wittenberg 2002-2011
 Member Editorial Board *Globalization* (University of Southern Colorado) 2001-
 Member Editorial Board *Applied Systems Studies: An International Journal on Methodologies and Applications for Systems Approaches* (Cambridge International Science Publishers) 1999-
 Member Advisory Board *Exemplaria: Revista Internacional de Literatura Comparada* (University of Huelva) 1998-2004
 Member Advisory Board Canadian Centre for Austrian and Central European Studies University of Alberta 1998-2000
 Member Executive Board International Association of Literary Semantics 1997-2006
 Vice-President International Association of Empirical Aesthetics 1997-2000
 Member Advisory Board *symplokē: a journal for the intermingling of literary, cultural and theoretical scholarship* (University of Nebraska Press) 1995-2015
 Member Executive Committee Hungarian Discussion Group Modern Language Association of America 1995-2000
 Chair Committee for Communication and Information International Comparative Literature Association / Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée 1994-1999
 President International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature / Internationale Gesellschaft für Empirische Literaturwissenschaften (IGEL) 1994-1996
 Member Executive Board Comparative Literature Association of Alberta 1989-1993
 Executive Secretary Board of Directors and Central and East European Studies Society of Alberta 1986-1988
 Member Executive Board Comparative Literature Graduate Students Association University of Alberta 1985-1989
 Member Executive Board Carleton University Arts Students Union 1981-1982
 President Arts Students Union University of Western Ontario 1977-1980
 External evaluation of PhD dissertations & MA theses, research projects, university department accreditation (selected): U of Halle-Wittenberg, European Commission, Erasmus Programme, Austrian Science Fund, Canadian Federation for the Humanities, U of Athens, Tel Aviv U, The Hebrew U of Jerusalem, National Defense Canada, Ghent U, Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada, The U of British Columbia Hampton Foundation, Complutense U Madrid, U of València, King Saud U, Romanian Academy of Sciences, Southern Illinois UP, Peking U, József Attila U, Wayne State UP, MIT Press, U of Sydney, Aristotle U, United Kingdom Arts and Humanities Research Board, International Comparative Literature Association, various learned journals
 Membership in academic organizations & associations 1984-: American Comparative Literature Association, Canadian Comparative Literature Association/Association Canadienne de Littérature Comparée (life member), American Hungarian Educators Association, Council of Editors of Learned Journals (USA), European Union Studies Association, International Association of Hungarian Studies, International Association of Empirical Aesthetics, International Comparative Literature Association/Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée, International Association for Media and Communication Research, International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature, Modern Language Association of America, Réseau Européen d'Etudes Littéraires Comparées/European Network for Comparative Literary Studies
 varia service (selected): Executive Board Hungarian Cultural Society Edmonton 1984-1987, Executive Board University of Alberta Michener Park Married Students Association 1984-1989, Carleton University Varsity Fencing Team 1980-1982, coach & team manager The University of Western Ontario Varsity Fencing Team 1976-1980

4) Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek's publications: 4.1 single-authored books / 4.2 edited volumes & journals / 4.3 articles, book chapters, encyclopedia entries, introductions / 4.4 bibliographies / 4.5 book reviews / 4.6 scholarly resources / 5. publications about Tötösy de Zepetnek's scholarship
 publications indexed in
 googlescholar <<https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=zH3x904AAAAJ>>
 ORCID: Connecting Research and Researchers <<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1506-0159>>
 semanticscholar <<https://www.semanticscholar.org/author/Steven-Tötösy-de-Zepetnek/1395825236>>
 Web of Science <<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/576342>>

4.1 single-authored books

4.1.6 Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. *Comparative Literature: Theory, Method, Application*. Amsterdam: Rodopi, 1998. ISBN 9042005343. 299 pages, bibliography, index. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2011): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/totosycomparativeliterature1998>>. The book contains a framework for comparative literature based on a contextual (systemic and empirical) approach for the study of literature and culture and applied in readership studies, film and literature, women's literature, translation studies, new media and scholarship in the humanities and in analyses of English, French, German, Austrian, Hungarian, Romanian, and English-Canadian modern, contemporary, and ethnic minority literature. Book reviews: Debarati Chakraborty, *Sāhitya: Journal of the Comparative Literature Association of India* 4-5 (2015): 122-27. Adnan K. Abdulla, *Babel* 49.4 (2003): 353-60. Dick Schram, *Frame: Tijdschrift voor Literatuurwetenschap* 15.1 (2001): 77-80. Marijan Dović, *Primerjalna književnost* 24.2 (2001): 114-19. Tomo Virk, *Primerjalna književnost* 24.2 (2001): 9-31. Nicolae Harsany, *symplokē: a journal for the intermingling of literary, cultural and theoretical scholarship* 7.1-2 (2000): 215. Elizabeth F. Dahab, *Journal of Caribbean Studies* 15.1-2 (2000): 299-302. Dolores Romero, *Signa: Revista de la Asociación Española Sabelthica* 9 (2000): 659-63. Jean-Marc Moura, *Revue de Littérature Comparée* 1 (2002): 97-98. Richard Cavell, *University of Toronto*

Quarterly: A Canadian Journal of Humanities 70.1 (2000-2001): 313. Priscilla Archibald, *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée* 27.1-2 (2000): 311-13. Camilla Miglio, *Observatorio critico della germanistica* 3.7 (2000): 18. Ernst Grabovszki, *Komparatistik: Jahrbuch der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Allgemeine und Vergleichende Literaturwissenschaft* (1999-2000): 168-73. Theodore Ziolkowski, *World Literature Today* 73.3 (1999): 606. Estelle Dansereau, *Ariel: A Review of International English Literature* 30.4 (1999): 168-71. Thomas Wägenbauer, *arcadia: Zeitschrift für Vergleichende Literaturwissenschaft* 37.2 (1999): 98-105. Joseph Pivato, *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* 1.4 (1999): 1-4. Hussam Alkhateeb, *Nizwa* 35.2 (1999): 75-81. Ernst Grabovszki, *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* 1.3 (1999): 1-5.

4.1.5 Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven (斯蒂文·托托西). *文学研究的合法化：一种新实用主义、整体化和经验主义文学与文化研究方法* (Legitimizing the Study of Literature: A New Pragmatism and the Systemic Approach to Literature and Culture). Trans. Jui-ch'i Ma / Ruiqi Ma (马瑞琪翻). Beijing: Peking University Press, 1997. ISBN 7301034822. 217 pages. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2011): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/legitimizingstudyofliterature>>. Contains chapters on radical constructivism, literary theory and methodology, women's writing, film and literature, and modern and contemporary prose.

4.1.4 Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. *The Social Dimensions of Fiction: On the Rhetoric and Function of Prefacing Novels in the Nineteenth-Century Canadas*. Wiesbaden: Friedr. Vieweg & Sohn, 1993. ISBN 3528073357. 188 pages, bibliography, index. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2009): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/totosystudyofpreface>>. Contains nineteenth-century English- and French-Canadian prefaces to novels & analyzed with theoretical and methodological frameworks for the study of rhetoric, the sociology of literature, readership studies, and genre studies. Book reviews: James Steele, *ESC: English Studies in Canada* 22.1 (1996): 117-19. Mary Lu MacDonald, *Canadian Literature* 148 (1996): 164-65. Carolyn Perkes, *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée* 23.2 (1996): 613-20. Vivienne J. Rundle, *Ariel: A Review of International English Literature* 26.3 (1995): 167-73. Robin Howells, *British Journal of Canadian Studies* 9.2 (1994): 437-38. Manuel Ribeiro, *Dedalus: Revista Portuguesa de Literatura Comparada* 3-4 (1993-94): 298-300.

4.1.3 Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. *Prefaces to Nineteenth-Century Canadian Novels: Their Function as Genre and Element of the Literary System*. Ph.D. Dissertation. Edmonton: University of Alberta, 1989. ISBN 0315556307. 317 pages, illustrations. Dissertation Abstracts International 1990 May v50.11, p3596A-3597A.

4.1.2 Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, comp. & ed. *nobilitashungariae: List of Historical Surnames of the Hungarian Nobility / A magyar történelmi nemesség családneveinek listája*. Genève: Zenodo, 2026- <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18808363>> ISSN 1923-9580. 128 pages, bibliography. Previous versions West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2010-2026 <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/nobilitashungariae>>. ISSN 1923-9580. Compilation of surnames based on historical sources (published and archival) of the Hungarian nobility with a selected list of published sources of Hungarian nobility and heraldry.

4.1.1 Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. *Records of the Tötösy de Zepetnek Family / A Zepetneki Tötösy család adattára*. Genève: Zenodo, 2026- <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18818592>> ISSN 1715-152X. Previous versions West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2010-2026 <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/totosyrecords>> ISSN 1715-152X. 403 pages, bibliography, index, illustrations. Contains transcripts of archival and family documents, sources and genealogies of Austrian, Belgian, Canadian, Croatian, Bohemian, Hungarian, Italian, Moravian, Romanian, Scottish, Slovak, and US-American families from the Middle Ages to current with selected English translations. First published *A Zepetneki Tötösy család adattára / Records of the Tötösy de Zepetnek Family*. Szeged: Attila József University, 1993. ISBN 9634819141 280 pages, bibliography, index, illustrations <<https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/totosyrecords1993>>. Book review: Szabolcs Vajay, *Turul: A Magyar Heraldikai és Genealógiai Társaság Közlöny*e (Turul: Publication of the Hungarian Society of Heraldry and Genealogy) 67.1-2 (1994): 56-57.

4.2 edited volumes & guest-edited special issues of learned journals

(● peer reviewed / x AHCI: Arts and Humanities Citation Indexed)

- x 4.2.35 2021. *Examples of the Formation and Variations of World Literature(s)*. Ed. Shunqing Cao and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Special Issue *Cultura: International Journal of Philosophy of Culture and Axiology* 18.1 (2021): 7-138.
- x 4.2.34 2015. *About Systemic and Empirical Approaches in the Study of Literature and Culture*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. *Comparative Literature* (American Comparative Literature Association & Duke University Press ISSN 0010-4124) 67.1 (2015): 1-44.
- x 4.2.33 2013. *Companion to Comparative Literature, World Literatures, and Comparative Cultural Studies*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Tutun Mukherjee. New Delhi: Cambridge University Press India, 2013. ISBN 9789382993667 538 pages, bibliography, index.
- x 4.2.32 2013. *Digital Humanities and the Study of Intermediality in Comparative Cultural Studies*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. West Lafayette: Purdue Scholarly Publishing Services, 2013. ISBN 9781626710023 383 pages, bibliography, index.
- x 4.2.31 2013. *New Work about World Literatures*. Ed. Graciela Boruszko and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Special Issue *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (Purdue University Press ISSN 1481-4374) 15.6 (2013): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweb/vol15/iss6/>>.
- x 4.2.30 2011. *New Perspectives on Material Culture and Intermedial Practice*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, Asunción López-Varela, Haun Saussy, and Jan Mieszkowski. Thematic Issue *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (Purdue University Press ISSN 1481-4374) 13.3 (2011): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweb/vol13/iss3/>>.
- 4.2.29 2011. *Comparative Hungarian Cultural Studies*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Louise O. Vasvári. West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2011. 9781557535931 376 pages, bibliography, index.
- 4.2.28 2010. *Mapping the World, Culture, and Border-crossing*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and I-Chun Wang. Kaohsiung: National Sun Yat-sen University Press, 2010. ISBN 9789860253863 162 pages, bibliography, index. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2014): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/mappingtheworld2010>>.
- 4.2.27 2010. *Perspectives on Identity, Migration, and Displacement*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, I-Chun Wang, and Hsiao-Yu Sun. Kaohsiung: National Sun Yat-sen University Press, 2010. ISBN 9789860235418 209 pages, bibliography, index. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2013): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/perspectivesonmigrationanddiaspora>>.
- 4.2.26 2009. *Cultural Discourse in Taiwan*. Ed. Chin-Chuan Cheng, I-Chun Wang, and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Kaohsiung: National Sun Yat-sen University Press, 2009. ISBN 9789860195064 239 pages, bibliography, index. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2014): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/taiwanculture2009>>.
- x 4.2.25 2009. *New Work in Holocaust Studies*. Ed. Louise O. Vasvári and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Thematic Issue *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (Purdue University Press ISSN 1481-4374) 11.1 (2009): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweb/vol11/iss1/>>.
- 4.2.24 2009. *Comparative Central European Holocaust Studies*. Ed. Louise O. Vasvári and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2009. ISBN 9781557535269 211 pages, bibliography, index.
- 4.2.23 2006. *The New Central and East European Culture*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, Carmen Andraş, and Magdalena Marsovszky. Aachen: Shaker Press, 2006. ISBN 383225143X 386 pages, bibliography, index.

- x 4.2.22 2005. *Comparative Cultural Studies and Michael Ondaatje's Writing*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2005. ISBN 1557533784 147 pages, bibliography, index.
- x 4.2.21 2005. *Imre Kertész and Holocaust Literature*. Ed. Louise O. Vasvári and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2005. ISBN 9781557533968 336 pages, bibliography, index.
- 4.2.20 2004. *Comparative Cultural Studies and Michael Ondaatje's Writing*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Thematic Issue *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (Purdue University Press ISSN 1481-4374) 6.3 (2004): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweb/vol6/iss3/>>.
- x 4.2.19 2003. *Comparative Literature and Comparative Cultural Studies*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2003. ISBN 1557532907 365 pages, bibliography, index.
- x 4.2.18 2002. *Comparative Central European Culture*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2002. ISBN 1557532400 217 pages, bibliography, index.
- 4.2.17 2000. *Histories and Concepts of Comparative Literature*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Thematic Issue *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (Purdue University Press ISSN 1481-4374) 2.4 (2000): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweb/vol2/iss4/>>.
- 4.2.16 1999. *Comparative Literature Now: Theories and Practice / La Littérature comparée à l'heure actuelle. Théories et réalisations*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, Milan V. Dimić, and Irene Sywenky. Paris: Honoré Champion, 1999. ISBN 2852036053 930 pages, bibliography.
- 4.2.15 1998. *Canadian Culture and Literatures, and a Taiwan Perspective*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Yiu-nam Leung. Edmonton: University of Alberta and Hsinchu: National Tsing Hua University, 1998. ISBN 0921490100 320 pages, bibliography. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2009): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/canadianculture/>>.
- 4.2.14 1997. *The Systemic and Empirical Approach to Literature and Culture as Theory and Application*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Irene Sywenky. Edmonton: University of Alberta and Siegen: Institute for Empirical Literature and Media Research, Siegen University, 1997. ISBN 0921490089 605 pages, bibliography, index. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2009): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/empiricalstudyofliterature/>>.
- 4.2.13 1997. *East Asian Cultural and Historical Perspectives: Histories and Society / Culture and Literatures*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Jennifer W. Jay. Edmonton: University of Alberta, 1997. ISBN 0921490097 383 pages, bibliography.
- 4.2.12 1996. *International Perspectives on Reading*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Special Issue *Reader: Essays in Reader-Oriented Theory, Criticism, and Pedagogy* (Michigan Technological University ISSN 0742-9681) 35-36 (1996): 1-120.
- 4.2.11 1996. *Comparative Literature: History and Contemporaneity / Littérature Comparée. Histoire et contemporanéité*. Ed. Milan V. Dimić and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Thematic Cluster *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée* (Canadian Comparative Literature Association ISSN 0319-051X) 23.1 (1996): 1-268.
- x 4.2.10 1996. *History of the Book and the Study of Literature*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. Thematic Cluster *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée* (Canadian Comparative Literature Association ISSN 0319-051X) 23.1 (1996): 207-58.
- 4.2.9 1996. *The Systemic and Empirical Approach to Literature: Theory and Application*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. *Literatura Comparada: Os Novos Paradigmas*. Ed. Margarida L. Losa, Ismênia de Sousa, and Gonçalo Vilas-Boas. Porto: Afrontamento, 1996. ISBN 9723604205 273-375 pages, bibliography.
- x 4.2.8 1995. *Postcolonial Literatures: Theory and Practice / Les Littératures post-coloniales. Théories et réalisations*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Sneja Gunew. Thematic Issue *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée* (Canadian Comparative Literature Association ISSN 0319-051X) 22.3-4 (1995): 399-932.
- 4.2.7 1994-97. *IGELnews: International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature* (ISSN 1203-2220). Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek. (1994): 1-55; (1995): 1-27; (1996): 1-14; (1997): 1-14.
- x 4.2.6 1993. *(Re)Vision(s) of Canadian Literature(s) / (Ré)vision(s) de(s)[la] littérature(s) canadienne(s)*. Ed. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Milan V. Dimić. Thematic Cluster *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée* (Canadian Comparative Literature Association ISSN 0319-051X) 20.3-4 (1993): 435-89.
- 4.2.5 1992. *IGEL Newsletter: International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature*. Ed. and comp. Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Art Graesser (International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature ISSN 1203-2220) 1 (1992): 1-24.
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- 1997. 乐黛云 (Yue, Daiyun). "序" ("Preface"). Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven (斯蒂文·托托西). *文学研究的合法化：一种新实用主义、整体化和经验主义文学与文化研究方法* (pp. 1-3) (Legitimizing the Study of Literature: A New Pragmatism and the Systemic Approach to Literature and Culture). Trans. 马瑞琪翻 (Jui-ch'i Ma). Beijing: Peking University Press, 1997. ISBN 7301034822. 217 pages. & *Library Series, CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* (2011): <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/clcweblibrary/legitimizingstudyofliterature>>.

6) external & internal funding for research, conference organization, publishing scholarship, awards

6.1 funding for research / 6.2 funding for conference organization / 6.3 funding for publishing scholarship / 6.4 awards

6.1 Funding received for research

Faculty research funding 2024-2029 Sichuan University US\$ 112,000.00 annually
 Research project 2011-2013: *Program for Interliteracy and Intermediality in Education* Ghent University Euros 12,500.00
 Research project 2009-2011: *Culture, Intermedialities, and Education, SIIM: Studies on Intermediality and Intercultural Mediation / Estudios sobre Intermedialidad como mediación intercultural* Complutense University Madrid & Ministry of Science and Innovation Spain Euros 3,000.00
 Faculty research funding 2008-2010: National Sun Yat-sen University NT\$ 70,000.00 annually
 Research project 2007-2008: *The Politics of Culture: Nationhood, Interculturalism, and Citizenship* Complutense University Madrid & Programa nacional de ayudas para la movilidad Spain Euros 27,000.00
 Team research project 2007-2008: *The Fantastic in Literature* Complutense University Madrid Euros 9,000.00
 Research project 2006: *Comparative Cultural Studies* University of Santiago de Compostela & Programa Mención de Calidad Spain Euros 9,000.00
 Research project 2006: *Nationalism and Interculturalities* National Sun Yat-sen University & Taiwan Ministry of Education US\$ 9,000.00
 Fellowship Senior Scholars 2000: Domus Hungarica Scientiarum et Artium & Hungarian Academy of Sciences US\$ 10,000.00
 Research and lectures 1999: Ministry of Science and Education Austria Can\$ 5,000.00
 Research and lectures 1996: PR of China Education Commission & Peking University Can\$ 1,500.00
 University of Alberta professorship in Chinese and Western Comparative Literature and Culture 1996-2003: Taiwan Chiang Ching-kuo Foundation for International Scholarly Exchange US\$ 350,000.00
 Research and lectures 1995: *Canadian Studies in China* P.R. of China & Cultural Personalities Exchange Program External Affairs Canada & International Trade Canada Can\$ 1,600.00
 Research and lectures 1995: Taiwan National Science Council Can\$ 4,000.00
 International representation 1992-1993: University of Alberta Can\$ 4,500.00
 International representation 1992-1994: Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council Canada Can\$ 11,500.00
 Team research project 1990-1992: *Problems in/of Canadian Ethnic Minority Writing* Secretary of State Canada Can\$ 88,000.00
 Research project 1989: *Urban Canadian Readership* University of Alberta Research Institute for Comparative Literature Can\$ 3,000.00
 Research project 1985-1987: *The History of the Edmonton Hungarian Cultural Society 1946-1986* Province of Alberta Canada Can\$ 2,000.00
 Graduate student research assistantship 1988-1989 University of Alberta Can\$ 24,000.00
 Research project 1983-1984: *A History of German-Canadian Literature* Secretary of State Canada Can\$ 9,500.00

6.2 funding received for conference organization

Literacy and Society, Culture, Media, & Education (with Ronald Soetaert) Ghent University 2012: Ghent University Euros 15,000.00
Atlantic Europe and the New Partnership (with Markus Vogt) University of Halle-Wittenberg 2004: University of Halle-Wittenberg, Franckesche Stiftungen Halle, Purdue University Press Euros 6,000.00
The Cultures of Post-1989 Central and East Europe (with Carmen Andraş and Magdalena Marsovszky) Georghé Şincai Institute 2003: Georghé Şincai Institute of the Social Sciences and Humanities Romanian Academy of Sciences, Purdue University Press, Austrian Science and Research Liaison Office, Petru Maior University, City of Targu Mureş Euros 30,000.00
Central European Culture Today: An Invitational International Conference (with Franz Szabo) University of Alberta 1999: University of Alberta Conference Fund, Ministry of Foreign Affairs Austria 26,000.00
Taiwan International Conference on Canadian Studies (with Yiu-nam Leung) National Tsing Hua University 1997: Canadian Trade Office, International Council for Canadian Studies, Canada Taipei Economic and Cultural Office, Taiwan Ministry of Education, & private sponsorship US\$ 50,000.00
4th Conference of the International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature University of Alberta 1996: University of Alberta President's Office, University of Alberta Conference Fund & Siegen University Institute for Empirical Literature and Media Research US\$ 10,000.00.
14th Triennial Congress of the International Comparative Literature Association (with Milan V. Dimić) University of Alberta 1994: Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada, Department of Heritage Canada, International Association of Canadian Studies, External Affairs Canada, University of Alberta Conference Fund, Gulbenkian Foundation Portugal, UNESCO US\$ 55,000.00
Conference on Language, Culture, and Literary Identity in Canada (with Michael Gnarowski) Carleton University 1984: Carleton University, Secretary of State Canada Can\$ 27,000.00

6.3 funding received for publishing scholarship

CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture 2000-2016: Purdue University & Purdue University Press (incl. Purdue graduate assistantships as editorial assistants): US\$ 15,000.00 annually
 Monograph series of "Books in Comparative Cultural Studies" 2002-2016: Purdue University & Purdue University Press US\$ 30,000.00 annually
Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée 1989-1997 (incl. University of Alberta graduate assistantships as journal editorial assistants): Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada Can\$ 45,000.00 annually
 Monograph series "Books in Comparative Literature" 1989-1997: Research Institute for Comparative Literature & Department of Comparative Literature University of Alberta Can\$ 25,000.00 annually

6.4 awards

The University of Alberta Hungarian Studies Scholarship 1986; The University of Alberta Henry Kreisel Scholarship in Canadian Literature 1985; The University of Western Ontario Dean's Honours List 1979

7) conference organization & participation

7.1 national & international conferences, seminars & panels organized / 7.2 conference papers, invited papers&lectures, plenary/keynote papers presented

7.1.30 2024. Zhuang, Peina (Sichuan University), and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek (Sichuan University), org. *Body Image(s) of Women in Literature*, panels, 24th Congress of the International Comparative Literature Association / Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée, Seoul, July-August 2025.
 7.1.29 2016. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, and Graciela Boruszko, org. *Digital Humanities in Comparative Literature, World Literature(s), and Comparative Cultural Studies*, panels, 21st Congress of the International Comparative Literature Association / Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée, University of Vienna, July 2016.
 7.1.28 2015. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, org. *Digital Humanities and Publishing Humanities Scholarship Today*, annual conference, NEMLA: Northeast Modern Language Association, Ryerson University, April 2015.

- 7.1.27 2012. Soetaert, Ronald, Kris Rutten, Geert Vandermeersche (Ghent University), and Steven Tötösý de Zepetnek, org., international conference *Literacy and Society, Culture, Media, & Education*, Ghent University, February 2012.
- 7.1.26 2011. Soetaert, Ronald, Kris Rutten, Geert Vandermeersche (Ghent University), and Steven Tötösý de Zepetnek, org., workshop, *Education, Culture, and Interliteracy: Aspects of Theory, Methodology, and Practice*, Ghent University, June 2011.
- 7.1.25 2011. Asunción López-Varela Azcárate (Complutense University Madrid), Steven Tötösý de Zepetnek, Tutun Mukherjee (University of Hyderabad), Christopher Larkosh (University of Massachusetts Dartmouth), and Agata Anna Lisiak (Berlin), org., international seminar, *The Other City*, Complutense University Madrid, May 2011.
- 7.1.24 2010. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, and Asunción López-Varela Azcárate (Complutense University Madrid), org., *Intermedialities in Comparative Cultural Studies*, panels, 19th Triennial Congress of the International Comparative Literature Association, Chung-Ang University, August 2010.
- 7.1.23 2009. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, I-Chun Wang (National Sun Yat-sen University), and Asunción López-Varela Azcárate (Complutense University Madrid), org., *Culture, Intermedialities, and Education*, conference seminars (three panels), annual conference, *American Comparative Literature Association 2009*, Harvard University, March 2009.
- 7.1.22 2008. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Publishing Scholarship in the Humanities and Social Sciences Today*, panel, international conference, *Perspectives on Migration, Nationhood and Ethnicity*, National Sun Yat-sen University, November 2008.
- 7.1.21 2006. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, and Louise O. Vasvári (Stony Brook University), org., *Comparative Cultural Studies*, international symposium, 6th International Congress of Hungarian Studies, University of Debrecen, August 2006.
- 7.1.20 2005. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Comparative Literature, Cultural Studies, and Comparative Cultural Studies*, conference seminar, annual conference, *American Comparative Literature Association 2005*, The Pennsylvania State University, March 2005.
- 7.1.19 2004. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, and Markus Vogt (Deutsche Bundeswehr Reservistenverband), org., *Atlantic Europe and the New Partnership*, University of Halle-Wittenberg, and Franckesche Stiftungen, February 2004.
- 7.1.18 2003. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Comparative Cultural Studies: Interculturalities and Culture Policy*, conference seminar, panels, international conference, *The Unifying Aspect of Cultures*, Research Institute for Austrian and International Literature and Cultural Studies, November 2003.
- 7.1.17 2003. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, Carmen Andraş (Georghe Şincai Institute), and Magdalena Marsovszky (Viadrina University), org., *The Cultures of Post-1989 Central and East Europe*, international conference, Georghe Şincai Institute and Petru Maior University, August 2003.
- 7.1.16 2002. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Comparative Cultural Studies 1: "Culture, Cultural Policy, and the Media," Comparative Cultural Studies 2: "Culture and Otherness," Comparative Cultural Studies 3: "Culture, Autobiography, and Translation," and Comparative Cultural Studies 4: "Aspects of Literature and Perspectives of Culture,"* conference seminar (four panels), *The Contemporaneity of the Non-Contemporaneous*, Research Institute for Austrian and International Literature and Cultural Studies, December 2002.
- 7.1.15 2002. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, and Reinhold Viehoff (U Halle-Wittenberg), org., *Comparative Cultural Studies*, conference panel, 8th biannual conference, *IGEL: International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature*, Janus Pannonius University, August 2002.
- 7.1.14 2000. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Comparative Cultural Studies and Post-1989 Central European Culture*, Hungarian Discussion Group, annual convention *Modern Language Association of America*, Washington DC, December 2000.
- 7.1.13 2000. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Comparative Cultural Studies: New Work in Psychology and Literature, New Media Scholarship, and the Appreciation of Art*, panel, 16th congress of the *International Association of Empirical Aesthetics*, New School University, August 2000.
- 7.1.12 1999. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Central European Culture Today: An Invitational International Conference*, Canadian Centre for Austrian and Central European Studies, University of Alberta and Embassy of Austria Ottawa, September 1999.
- 7.1.11 1999. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Comparative Culture and Hungarian Studies*, 24th annual conference, *American Hungarian Educators' Association*, John Carroll University, Cleveland, USA, April 1999.
- 7.1.10 1998. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, and Aldo Nemesio (U of Torino), org., *Methodology and the Study of Literature and Culture*, panel, 15th biannual congress of the *IAEA: International Association of Empirical Aesthetics*, University of Rome La Sapienza, September 1998.
- 7.1.9 1997. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Theoretical and Methodological Innovation in the Study of Literature: The Systemic and Empirical Approach to Literature and Culture*, panel, 15th Triennial Congress International Comparative Literature Association, Leiden University, August 1997.
- 7.1.8 1997. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, and Yiu-nam Leung (National Tsing Hua University), org., 1997 International Conference on *Canadian Studies*, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan, April 1997.
- 7.1.7 1996. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven. *Teaching Literature on the Internet*, panel, 5th international symposium and book fair of *The English Teachers' Association*, National Taiwan Normal University, November 1996.
- 7.1.6 1996. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., 5th biannual conference, *IGEL: International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature*, University of Alberta, August 1996.
- 7.1.5 1995. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Simpósio da Associação Internacional para o Estudo Empírico da Literatura*, Comparative Literature Association of Portugal, University of Porto, May 1995.
- 7.1.4 1994. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Reading and Readership: Theories, Application, Practice / Lecture et lecteur(e)s. Théories, application, pratique*, 14th triennial congress, *International Comparative Literature Association*, University of Alberta, August 1994.
- 7.1.3 1994. Dimić, Milan V. (University of Alberta), and Steven Tötösý de Zepetnek, org., 14th Triennial Congress of the *International Comparative Literature Association*, University of Alberta, August 1994.
- 7.1.2 1991. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, org., *Early Twentieth-Century Hungarian Feminist Literature*, panel, 3rd World Congress of *Hungarian Studies*, Attila József University, Szeged, Hungary, August 1991.
- 7.1.1 1984. Gnarowski, Michael (Carleton University), and Steven Tötösý de Zepetnek (Carleton University), org., *Conference on Language, Culture, and Literary Identity in Canada*, Carleton University, May 1984.
- 7.2 conference papers, (invited) public lectures, and plenary/keynote papers presented
- 7.2.164 2026. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven. "Urban Spaces and Transformations in/of Western Society," public lecture, College of Literature, Sichuan University, June 2026.
- 7.2.163 2026. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven. "About the History of Comparative Literature in Hungary," public lecture, College of Literature, Sichuan University, May 2026.
- 7.2.162 2026. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven, and Zhuang, Peina. "Comparative Literature across the World in 2026," paper, ESCL: European Society of Comparative Literature, University of Leeds, August 2026.
- 7.2.161 2025. Zhuang, Peina, and Steven Tötösý de Zepetnek. "From 'Technical Borrowing' to 'Paradigmatic Reconstruction': Digital Humanities and Critical Reflections in Chinese Comparative Literature Studies" paper, international conference *Comparative Literature and Interdisciplinarity*, University of Pécs, December 2025.
- 7.2.160 2025. Tötösý de Zepetnek, Steven. "Towards a Theoretical Framework for Analyses of Body Images of Women in Literature," paper, *Body Image(s) of Women in Literature*, panels (org. Peina Zhuang and Steven Tötösý de Zepetnek), 24th Congress of the *International Comparative Literature Association / Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée*, Seoul, July-August 2025.

- 7.2.159 2025. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Digital Humanities and Publishing Scholarship in the Humanities," paper, Research Committee on Digital Comparative Literature, 24th Congress of the International Comparative Literature Association / Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée, Seoul, July-August 2025.
- 7.2.158 2025. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Pre-1900 German-Canadian Ethnic Minority Writing," public lecture, College of Literature and Journalism, Sichuan University, June 2025.
- 7.2.157 2025. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Nobel 2002 Imre Kertész and Contemporary Hungarian Culture," public lecture, College of Literature and Journalism, Sichuan University, June 2025.
- 7.2.156 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Digital Humanities and the Study of Literature and Culture Today," invited lecture, College of Journalism, Nanjing University, November 2024.
- 7.2.155 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Ethical Literary Criticism, Semiotics, and Comparative Cultural Studies," keynote paper, 2024 Nanjing Semiotics Conference, Nanjing University, November 2024.
- 7.2.154 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Digital Humanities and the Study of Literature and Culture Today," public lecture, College of Literature and Journalism, Sichuan University, November 2024.
- 7.2.153 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Theoretical Perspectives and 'Ethnic' Literatures in Canada." invited paper, 第二届中华文化天府论坛 2024 年 10 月 29-31 日 (Chinese Culture Tianfu Forum 29-31 October 2024), Chengdu, October 2024.
- 7.2.152 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Michael Ondaatje's *The English Patient*: Novel and Film," invited paper, Canadian Research Centre, College of Literature and Journalism, Sichuan University, October 2024.
- 7.2.151 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Kafka Margit önéletrajza" ("Margit Kafka's Life Writings"), invited paper, Annual Conference, Gender Studies Research Group (Department of English), University of Szeged, October 2024.
- 7.2.150 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Discipline of Comparative Literature in Hungarian Scholarship," invited paper, Magyar Tudományos Akadémia / Hungarian Academy of Sciences, October 2024.
- 7.2.149 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Discipline of Comparative Literature in Hungarian Scholarship," invited paper, international conference *The History of Comparative Literature in Central Europe*, University of Ljubljana, September 2024.
- 7.2.148 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "From Comparative Literature towards Comparative Cultural Studies: New Perspectives," public lecture, College of Literature and Journalism, Sichuan University, April 2024.
- 7.2.147 2024. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "From Comparative Literature toward Comparative Cultural Studies: New Perspectives," invited lecture, Shaanxi Normal University, March 2024.
- 7.2.146 2023. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Csicseri Orosz Adrienne (1878-1934) szerelmes levelei Prohászka Ottokárhoz" ("About the Love Letters of Adrienne Orosz de Csicsér [1878-1934] to Bishop Ottokár Prohászka"), paper, Annual Conference, Gender Studies Research Group (Department of English), University of Szeged, September 2023.
- 7.2.145 2022. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Nobel 2002 Imre Kertész and Holocaust Literature," invited paper, Department of English, University of Regina, September 2022.
- 7.2.144 2021. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Ondaatje's *The English Patient*: Novel and Film," invited paper, Humanities Conferences Online 2020-2021, Sichuan University, October 2021.
- 7.2.143 2021. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About Comparative Literature, Cultural Studies, and Comparative Cultural Studies," invited paper, Humanities Conferences Online 2020-2021, Sichuan University, September 2021.
- 7.2.142 2021. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Literature and the Last Two Decades," invited paper, University of Georgia (USA), April 2021.
- 7.2.141 2021. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About Comparative Literature, Comparative Cultural Studies, and World Literature(s)," invited paper, Delhi Comparatists' Comparative Literature Forum (online), Jadavpur University, March 2021.
- 7.2.140 2021. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Peripherality: 'Minor' Literatures, Women's Literature, and Orosz's Novels," invited paper, Humanities Conferences Online 2020-2021, Sichuan University, February 2021.
- 7.2.139 2017. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Data Science and the Study of Literature," invited paper, Annual Conference of the Chinese Comparative Literature Association, University of Henan, August 2017.
- 7.2.138 2017. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Literature Journals and the Relevance of Publishing Online," invited paper, *Comparative Literature: Tracing Journals in India and the World* (Debashree Dattaray and Suchorita Chattopadhyay, org.), Jadavpur University, March 2017.
- 7.2.137 2016. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Digital Humanities, Data Science, and the Study of Literature," paper, panel *Digital Humanities in Comparative Literature, World Literature(s), and Comparative Cultural Studies* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Graciela Boruszko, org.), 21st Congress of the International Comparative Literature Association / Association Internationale de Littérature Comparée, University of Vienna, July 2016.
- 7.2.136 2016. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Digital Humanities and Publishing Scholarship in Electronic Journals," invited paper, *What Do Comparative Literature and Digital Humanities Have To Say To Each Other?: A Critical Approach* (Sayan Bhattacharyya and Fatma Tarlaci, org.), annual conference, *American Comparative Literature Association*, Harvard University, March 2016.
- 7.2.135 2015. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "New Media and Publishing in the Humanities" & "Women's Writing and Social Commitment," invited public lectures, Central China Normal University, October 2015.
- 7.2.134 2015. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Ethical Literary Criticism, Semiotics, and Comparative Cultural Studies," invited keynote paper, *First International Symposium on Cultural & Communication Semiotics*, Sichuan University, July 2015.
- 7.2.133 2015. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Digital Humanities and the Publishing of CLCWeb: *Comparative Literature and Culture 1999-*," paper, panel *Digital Humanities and Publishing Humanities Scholarship Today*, annual conference *NEMLA: Northeast Modern Language Association*, Ryerson University, April 2015.
- 7.2.132 2015. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Kafka Margit (1888-1918) munkájának mai fontossága" ("The Relevance of Margit Kafka's [1888-1918] Work Today"), invited paper, TudósKlub (Scholars Club), Association of Boston Hungarians, Boston, January 2015.
- 7.2.131 2015. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "How to Create an Electronic Journal in the Humanities," invited paper, panel *Journal Editing 101: An Introduction to the Role of Editor* (Sol Miguel-Prendes, org.), annual convention *Modern Language Association of America*, Vancouver, January 2015.
- 7.2.130 2014. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Margit Kafka (1880-1918) and World War I." paper, *Representing World War I: Perspectives at the Centenary* (Daniel Hamby, org.), Humber College, October 2014.
- 7.2.129 2014. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Heraldry in the Kingdom of Hungary," invited plenary paper Wilkes Lecture, Royal Heraldry Society of Canada / La Société Royale Héraldique du Canada, Toronto, May 2014.
- 7.2.128 2014. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About Publishing a Ph.D. Dissertation as a Book," invited paper, *Workshop Publishing Your First Book: Tips from Writers, Editors, and Publishers*, annual conference, *American Comparative Literature Association*, New York University, March 2014.
- 7.2.127 2013. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About Humanities Education in the West," invited public lecture, Central China Normal University, November 2013.
- 7.2.126 2013. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About Humanities Situation of Education in the West" & "Alterity and Ethnic Minority Studies," invited public lectures, Sichuan University, November 2013.
- 7.2.125 2013. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Impact of New Media on Academic Book and Journal Publishing in the Humanities," invited paper, symposium, *6th Sino-American Symposium*, Purdue University, May 2013.
- 7.2.124 2013. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "A humántudományok helyzete és a jelenlegi kultúra kutatás" ("Sustainable Humanities and the Study of Culture Today"), invited paper, international conference, *Holistics and Complex Thought for a Sustainable Humanist Future / A fenntartható fejlődés emberközpontú holisztikus megközelítése*, UNESCO-UNITWIN, Centre Européen de la Culture, International Association of Hungarian Professors, Budapesti Gazdasági Főiskola/Budapest Business School, Budapest,

March 2013.

7.2.123 2013. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About the Difference between Comparative Literature and World Literature," invited paper, panel *Perspectivizing World Literature*, annual convention *Modern Language Association of America* (Marko Juvan, org.), Boston, January 2013.

7.2.122 2012. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About the Study of Hungarian Culture as Comparative Central European Cultural Studies," invited paper, symposium, Canadian-Hungarian Studies Association, *Crossroads: Scholarship for an Uncertain World*, annual conference Canadian Federation of the Humanities and Social Sciences, Wilfrid Laurier University & University of Waterloo, May 2012.

7.2.121 2012. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Kertész and Márai as (Im)migrant Writers," invited paper, *Hungarian Borders, (Im)migrations, Diasporas*, annual conference, American Hungarian Educators Association, Long Island University Brooklyn, New York, April 2012.

7.2.120 2012. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Digital Humanities and Interculturality," invited paper, international conference, *Literacy and Society, Culture, Media, & Education*, Ghent University, February 2012.

7.2.119 2012. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About the Social Relevance of the Study of Culture and Literature," invited public lecture, Purdue University, January 2011.

7.2.118 2011. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Aspects of Migration in Péter Nádas's *A Book of Memories*," invited paper, international conference, *The Journey and Its Portrayals: Explorers, Sailors, (Im)migrants*, National Sun Yat-sen University, November 2011.

7.2.117 2011. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, "The Other City and Emergent Urban Cultures," invited paper, international workshop *The Other City*, Complutense University Madrid, May 2011.

7.2.116 2011. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, "Strategies and Processes of Publishing Scholarship in the Humanities and Social Sciences Today" & "Comparative Cultural Studies and the Notions of the 'Contextual,' the 'Comparative,' the 'Empirical,' and the 'Interdisciplinary'," seminars, Faculty of Psychology and Education, Ghent University, April 2011.

7.2.115 2010. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, and Agata Anna Lisiak (Berlin), "Literary Representations of Post-1989 Urban Spaces of Berlin, Budapest, and Warsaw," invited paper, international seminar, *Narrativity and the Perception / Conception of Landscape*, Ghent University, December 2010.

7.2.114 2010. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Scharang's Documentary Film *Tintenfischalarm* (2006)," invited paper, international workshop *Literature, Hermaphrodite: Intersections of Writing, Culture and Media*, Complutense University Madrid, November 2010.

7.2.113 2010. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The 'Impact Factor' and Selected Issues of Content and Technology in Humanities Scholarship Published Online," invited public lecture, University of Liverpool, May 2010.

7.2.112 2010. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Travel in Péter Nádas's *A Book of Memories*," invited paper, *4th Annual Liverpool Travel Seminar*, John Moores University, May 2010.

7.2.111 2010. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Literature, World Literature, and (Comparative) Cultural Studies" & "The 'Impact Factor' and Selected Issues of Content and Technology in Humanities Scholarship Published Online," invited paper, Kuwait University, March 2010.

7.2.110 2009. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Interdisciplinarity and the Importance of New Media Publishing of Scholarship in the Humanities," invited paper, Annual meeting of Taiwan Research Centers for the Humanities, National Sun Yat-sen University, November 2009.

7.2.109 2009. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Towards a Theory and Its Application in the Study of Diaspora and Ethnic Literature(s)." *Mapping the World: Migration and Border-Crossing*, paper, international conference, National Sun Yat-sen University, October 2009.

7.2.108 2009. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Jews and Roma in Post-1989 Austria and Hungary," invited plenary paper, *Genocide, Forced Labor, and World War II in Central and East Europe / Völkermord, Zwangsarbeit und der Zweiter Weltkrieg in Mittel- und Osteuropa*, international conference, Stiftung Denkmal für die ermordeten Juden Europas & Stiftung Erinnerung, Verantwortung und Zukunft, Berlin, September 2009.

7.2.107 2009. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Intermediality and Its Promise towards Interculturalism," invited keynote paper, *Multiculturalism in the Americas and Great Britain: Comparative Perspectives*, international conference, University of Bielefeld, July 2009.

7.2.106 2009. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, and Agata Anna Lisiak (U of Halle-Wittenberg), "Intermediality and Cyber Visualities of Central European Cities," invited paper, *Actual and Virtual Cities: Intertextuality and Intermediality / Cités réelles. Cités virtuelles (intertextualité et intermédialité)* (Asunción López-Varela Azcárate and Mariana Net, org.), International Summer School for Semiotic Studies: Pan-European Culture Heritage in the Global World, Imatra, June 2009.

7.2.105 2009. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Education, Interculturalism, and the New Europe," invited keynote paper, *Ideas of Europe / Ideas for Europe*, international conference, Chemnitz University of Technology, May 2009.

7.2.104 2009 Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Education, Interculturalism, and New Media," paper, seminar *Culture, Intermedialities, and Education* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, I-Chun Wang, and Asunción López-Varela Azcárate, org.), annual conference, *American Comparative Literature Association* 2009, Harvard University, March 2009.

7.2.103 2009. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Social Relevance of the Study of Culture and Literature, Intercultural Communication, and Sustainable Humanities," invited keynote paper, *Diverse Harmonies: Literary and Cultural Confluences*, biennial conference, Comparative Literature of India Association, University of Hyderabad, January 2009.

7.2.102 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Issues of Technology and Content in Publishing Scholarship Online," invited paper, roundtable *What is a Scholarly Journal? Identity Issues in Our Digital Age*, annual convention *Modern Language Association of America*, San Francisco, December 2008.

7.2.101 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Selected Aspects of Digital Scholarship in Comparative Humanities and Social Sciences," invited paper, roundtable *Evaluating and Publishing Comparative Scholarship: A Roundtable with Journal Editors*, annual convention *Modern Language Association of America*, San Francisco, December 2008.

7.2.100 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Literature, Comparative Cultural Studies, and the Social Relevance of the Humanities Today," invited lecture, National University of Kaohsiung, December 2008.

7.9.99 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Az összehasonlító kultúrákutatók legújabb kérdései" ("New Developments in Comparative Cultural Studies"), invited public lecture, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, November 2008.

7.2.98 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Education, Interculturalism, and the New Europe," paper, annual conference, Hungarian Association of Sociology, University of Pannonia, November 2008.

7.2.97 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Humanities Scholarship and Academic Publishing Today," invited paper and panel moderator, *Perspectives on Migration, Nationhood and Ethnicity*, international conference, National Sun Yat-sen University, November 2008.

7.2.96 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Publishing Humanities Scholarship Online, Interculturalism, and Distance Education," invited paper, international workshop *E-learning and Multicultural Education: Digital Divide and Digital Opportunities*, Association of Global Universities in Distance Education, University of Technology Guglielmo Marconi, May 2008.

7.2.95 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Publishing Humanities Scholarship Online," paper, *Conference of the Society for Textual Scholarship*, The Editorial Institute, Boston University, March 2008.

7.2.94 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Intercultural Communication and Sustainable Humanities: Toward the Social Relevance of the Study of Culture and Literature," invited plenary paper, *Crossing the Literary Divide: English-Arabic Comparative Literature*, Qatar University & Georgetown University, March 2008.

- 7.2.93 2008. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Current Situation of Anti-Semitism and Anti-Other in Hungary, Austria, and the Former East Germany," invited public lecture, Faculty of Arts, Northeastern U, Boston, Massachusetts, USA, February 2008.
- 7.2.92 2007. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "About Eroticism in Hungarian Culture," paper, annual conference, American Hungarian Educators Association, New York, April 2007.
- 7.2.91 2006. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Towards a New Framework in the Humanities as Comparative Cultural Studies," "Translation Studies and Interculturalism," and "The Politics of Culture: Nationhood, Interculturalism, and Citizenship," invited paper, National Sun Yat-sen University, National Kaohsiung Normal University, National Kaohsiung University, and I-Shou University, November 2006.
- 7.2.90 2006. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Literature and Translation Studies as Interculturalism," invited plenary paper, *Traducción y multiculturalismo*, internaional conference, University of Alicante, November 2006.
- 7.2.89 2006. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The 1956 Hungarian Revolution and Its Cultural Expressions in Canada: Film," invited paper, *The 1956 Hungarian Revolution 50 Years Later: Canadian and International Perspectives*, international conference, University of Ottawa and Secretary of State Canada, October 2006.
- 7.2.88 2006. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Scholarship and Publishing in the Age of New Media Technology," invited plenary paper, *Las Literaturas del Texto al Hipertexto / Literatures from Text to Hypertext*, international conference, Complutense University Madrid, September 2006.
- 7.2.87 2006. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Imre Kertész and Contemporary Hungarian Literature," invited paper, Department of Slavic Literatures, University of North Carolina Chapel Hill, September 2006.
- 7.2.86 2006. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The New Humanities: The Intercultural, the Comparative, and the Interdisciplinary," invited plenary paper, *Corrientes actuales de la Teoría literaria en España*, postgraduate seminar, University of Málaga, July 2006.
- 7.2.85 2006. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Visualities of the Holocaust in the Work of Imre Kertész, Novel and Film," paper, panel *Comparative Cultural Studies* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Louise O. Vasvári, org.), *6th International Congress of Hungarian Studies*, University of Debrecen, August 2006.
- 7.2.84 2005. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The New Humanities: The Intercultural, the Comparative, and the Interdisciplinary," invited plenary paper, *II Congresso Internacional de Estudos Comparativos*, University Estadual da Paraíba, August 2005.
- 7.2.83 2005. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Culture and Culture Policy in Post-1989 Central Europe: The European Union, Germany, Austria, Hungary, and Romania," paper, *Looking Forward-Looking Back: The AHEA at Thirty*, 30th Anniversary Conference of the American Hungarian Educators Association, Central European University, June 2005.
- 7.2.82 2005. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Literature versus or with Cultural Studies," paper, panel *Comparative Literature, Cultural Studies, and Comparative Cultural Studies* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), annual conference, *American Comparative Literature Association*, The Pennsylvania State University, March 2005.
- 7.2.81 2004. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Cultural Studies, Theoretical Frameworks, and Institutional Administration in the Humanities," invited plenary paper, *Conference on Textual Ambiguity*, international conference, University of Sydney, August 2004.
- 7.2.80 2004. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Profile Groups and Cultural Participation with Mass Media in the USA and in Germany 2001-2003," paper, second annual conference, Cultural Studies Association (USA), Northeastern University, May 2004.
- 7.2.79 2004. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "A Comparative Analysis of Cultural Participation with Mass Media in the US and Germany 2001-2003," paper, *Communication and All That Jazz*, 8th annual conference, New Jersey Communication Association, Rutgers University, March 2004.
- 7.2.78 2004. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The European Union Armed Forces in the Media," paper, *Atlantic Europe and the New Partnership* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Markus Vogt, org.), international conference, University of Halle-Wittenberg, February 2004.
- 7.2.77 2003. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Culture and Culture Policy in Post-1989 Central and East Europe," paper, workshop panel *Comparative Cultural Studies: Interculturalities and Culture Policy* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), *The Unifying Aspect of Cultures*, international conference, Research Institute for Austrian and International Literature and Cultural Studies, November 2003.
- 7.2.76 2003. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Kultur und Kulturpolitik in Mitteleuropa nach 1989," invited plenary paper, *Zwischen-europa / Mitteleuropa. Sprache und Literatur in interkultureller Konstellation*, international conference, Technical University Dresden, October 2003.
- 7.2.75 2003. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Imre Kertész and the 2002 Nobel Prize in Literature in the German, Hungarian, and the US and Canadian Media," paper, *The Cultures of Post-1989 Central and East Europe: An International Conference* (Carmen Andraş, Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, and Magdalena Marsovszky, org.), international conference, Georghie Şincai Institute of the Romanian Academy of Sciences, Petru Maior University, and the City of Targu Mureş, August 2003.
- 7.2.74 2003. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Imre Kertész and the 2002 Nobel Prize in Literature in the German and Hungarian Media," invited paper, 28th annual conference, *American Hungarian Educators Association*, Columbia University, April 2003.
- 7.2.73 2003. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "An Introduction to Queer Theory in Culture and Literature Studies," invited public lecture, Faculty of Arts, University of Halle-Wittenberg, January 2003.
- 7.2.72 2002. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Minor Cultures, National Culture, and the Administration of Culture," paper, panel *Interculturality, Multiculturalism, and Comparative Cultural Studies* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), international conference of the Research Institute for Austrian and International Literature and Cultural Studies, Wien, December 2002.
- 7.2.71 2002. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "A View at Media Consumption of University Students in the USA and Germany Today" and "Comparative Humanities in the Twenty-First Century," invited lectures, Ghent University, November 2002.
- 7.2.70 2002. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven, Reinhold Viehoff, Clemens Seyfried, and Konstanze Wunneburg. "A Comparative Analysis of Media Consumption and Cultural Participation in the US and Germany Today (work-in-progress)," invited paper, panel *Comparative Cultural Studies* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Reinhold Viehoff, org.) *8th Biannual Conference International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature*, Janus Pannonius University, August 2002.
- 7.2.69 2002. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Buntes Kanada. Ethisches Mosaik" ("Colourful Canada: Mosaic of Ethnicity"), invited paper, German-Canadian Association, Halle, June 2002.
- 7.2.68 2002. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "New Media Technology and the Humanities," invited public lecture, Faculty of Arts, Florida Atlantic University, February 2002.
- 7.2.67 2000. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Cultural Studies and Post-1989 Central European Culture," paper, panel *Comparative Cultural Studies and Post-1989 Central European Culture*, Hungarian Discussion Group (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), annual convention *Modern Language Association of America*, Washington D.C., December 2000.
- 7.2.66 2000. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Literature Today, Comparative Cultural Studies Tomorrow, and New Media Scholarship," invited public lecture, University of Connecticut, October 2000.
- 7.2.65 2000. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "New Media Scholarship in the Humanities and Social Sciences," paper, panel *Comparative Cultural Studies: New Work in Psychology and Literature, New Media Scholarship, and the Appreciation of Art* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), *International Association of Empirical Aesthetics*, international conference, New School University, August 2000.
- 7.2.64 2000. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Central European Life Writing in the United States and Canada," invited paper, *European Integration and the Changes in European Boundary Constructions: Collective Identities, Citizenship, and Europeaness in Western and Eastern Europe*, international conference, European University Institute (Italy), April 2000.
- 7.2.63 2000. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "New Media Scholarship and the Humanities," invited paper, *Linguaggi e siti: la storia on line*, international conference, Department of History and Civilization, University of Firenze, April 2000.

- 7.2.62 1999. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "A Taxonomy of Central European Culture," invited paper, *Central European Culture Today*, international conference, Canadian Centre for Austrian and Central European Studies, University of Alberta, September 1999.
- 7.2.61 1999. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Toward Comparative Cultural Studies" and "LiteraturEN in Kanada. Ein Überblick," invited lecture tour, universities of Innsbruck, Wien, Graz, Klagenfurt, and Ministry of Education and Science Austria, June 1999.
- 7.2.60 1999. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Central European Cultural Identity, Diasporas, and Jewish-Hungarian Women's Writing," paper, panel *Comparative Culture and Hungarian Studies* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), 24th annual conference, *American Hungarian Educators' Association*, John Carroll University, April 1999.
- 7.2.59 1998. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Literary and Filmic Representations of the Titanic Disaster," *Poseidon and the Muses: Arts, Literature, and the Ocean: An International Conference* and "The Discipline of Comparative Literature: Toward and Intellectual and Institutional History," invited lectures, National Sun Yat-Sen University, December 1998.
- 7.2.58 1998. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Discipline of Comparative Literature: Toward an Intellectual and Institutional History" and "Comparative Literature in Canada: Toward an Intellectual and Institutional History," invited guest lectures, Beijing Language and Culture University, December 1998.
- 7.2.57 1998. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Die ungarische Revolution in 1956 und ihre Spiegelung in Exilliteratur," invited guest lecture, University of Leipzig, June 1998.
- 7.2.56 1998. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The 1956 Hungarian Revolution in Literature: Aspects of Exile, Memory, and Shifting Perspectives," invited paper, panel *War and Memory: Historical Transmission and Cultural Representation* (Susan Rubin Suleiman and Marianne Hirsch, org.), annual conference, *American Comparative Literature Association*, University of Texas Austin, March 1998.
- 7.2.55 1998. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Necessity of Method in the Study and Teaching of Literature," paper, panel *Method and the Study and Teaching of Literature* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek and Aldo Nemesio, org.), *Congress of the International Association of Empirical Aesthetics*, University of Rome La Sapienza, Roma, Italy, September 1998.
- 7.2.54 1997. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "How is Comparative Literature?," invited guest lecture, University of Oklahoma, December 1997.
- 7.2.53 1997. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "A Theory of Inbetween Peripherality and Its Application to Diasporic Literatures," paper, panel *Postmodernities and Ethnic Minority Writing: Theory and Application / Post-modernités et la littérature minoritaire ethnique. Théories et réalisations* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), *15th Triennial Congress International Comparative Literature Association*, Leiden University, August 1997.
- 7.2.52 1997. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The English Patient Reconsidered: Aspects of Media and Public Discourse," paper, panel *Theoretical and Methodological Innovation in the Study of Literature: The Systemic and Empirical Approach to Literature and Culture* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), *15th Triennial Congress International Comparative Literature Association*, August 1997.
- 7.2.51 1997. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Toward a History of the *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature / Revue Canadienne de Littérature Comparée, 1974-96*," invited paper, panel *Empirical Research on Literature* (Aldo Nemesio, org.) at the *International Association of Literary Semantics*, University of Freiburg, September 1997.
- 7.2.50 1997. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Social Discourse and Cultural Participation in a Multicultural Society," paper, *Taiwan International Conference on Canadian Studies* (Yiu-nam Leung and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), National Tsing Hua University, April 1997.
- 7.2.49 1996. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "New Developments in Neuroscience and Brain Research with Reference to Language Acquisition and the Teaching of Foreign Languages," invited paper, *5th International Conference of the English Teachers' Association of the Republic of China*, National Taiwan Normal University, November 1996.
- 7.2.48 1996. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Translation of Literature: Theory and Application," paper and workshop, invited paper, National Taiwan Normal University, November 1996.
- 7.2.47 1996. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Reader-Response to Authorial Gender Specificity in the Narrative of Pornographic Literature," invited paper, 5th biannual conference, *International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), University of Alberta, August 1996.
- 7.2.46 1996. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Recent Impressions of the Intellectual and Institutional Situation of the Study of Literature and Literary Theory in China and Taiwan," invited paper, annual conference, *Asian Studies on the Pacific Coast*, University of Alberta, June 1996.
- 7.2.45 1996. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Philosophy and Literature: The Former East Germany and Hungary Today," invited paper, panel *Agonistic Imagination: Literature and Philosophy in the Postcommunist Restructuring of Eastern Europe* (Christian Moraru, org.), 20th annual conference, *International Association for Philosophy and Literature*, George Mason University, May 1996.
- 7.2.44 1996. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Legitimizing the Study of Literature" and "Systemic Approaches to Literature and Culture" (National Tsing Hua University), "Legitimizing the Study of Literature" (National Chiao Tung University), and "The Problematics of Cultural Identity and/in Literature" (Fu Jen Catholic University), invited lecture tour, National Science Council, Taiwan, April 1996.
- 7.2.43 1996. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Postcolonial Literature and Ethnic Minority Writing," "Comparative Literature: New Trends in Theory and Method," "Applications in a New Comparative Literature," and "A Description of Comparative Literature and the Study of Literature in Canada Today: Intellectual and Institutional Positions," invited public lectures, Peking University, April 1996.
- 7.2.42 1996. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Cultural Studies and Comparative Literature: A World View for the Study of Literature and Culture," invited guest lecture, Beijing Normal University, April 1996.
- 7.2.41 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Narrative of Change in East Central Europe: A New Marginality?," invited paper, panel *Postmodern Thought and Prepostmodern Cultures* (Marcel Cornis-Pope, org.), annual convention *Modern Language Association of America*, Chicago, December 1995.
- 7.2.40 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Institution of English: System, Cultural Diversity, and Pedagogy," invited paper, *4th International Symposium of the English Teachers' Association of the Republic of China*, National Kaohsiung Normal University, November 1995.
- 7.2.39 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Literature and Translation: The Importance of Methodology," invited public lecture, National Chung Cheng University, November 1995.
- 7.2.38 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Cultural Identity and Economic Performance in Central Europe: Austria and Hungary," invited paper, *Conference on European Cultural Identity*, University of Halle-Wittenberg, November 1995.
- 7.2.37 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Importance of Cultural Dialogue: A Case Study of Ethnic Minority Writing and Cultural Participation in Canada," invited paper, *International Conference on Cultural Dialogue and Cultural Misreading*, Peking University, October 1995.
- 7.2.36 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Translation Theories Applied: The Nitra School, the Polysystem Theory, and the Systemic and Empirical Approach to Literature," invited guest lecture, Department of English, Peking University, October 1995.
- 7.2.35 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Life Writing of German-Canadian Pioneer Else Seel 1894-1974," invited paper, *7th International Conference of the British Comparative Literature Association*, University of Edinburgh, July 1995.
- 7.2.34 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Factors in a Theory of Cumulative Canon Formation: Contemporary Hungarian and English-Canadian Literature," invited paper, *Simpósio da Associação Internacional para o Estudo Empírico da Literatura* (Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), international conference, *Associação Portuguesa de Literatura Comparada*, University of Porto, May 1995.

- 7.2.33 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Multikulturalismus, ethnische Literaturen und kanadische Identität," invited guest lecture, Department of Media and Communication Studies, University of Halle-Wittenberg, March 1995.
- 7.2.32 1995. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Canadian Literatures" (Gáspár Károli University), "Literary Theory and the Information Revolution," "The Canadian Cultural Industry and Literary Reading" (Attila József University), "The Politics of Education and the Modern U" (University of Pécs), invited public lectures, March-April 1995.
- 7.2.31 1994. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "*Extra Hungariam (non)est vita*: Political Satire in Hungarian Exile Literature," invited paper, annual convention *Modern Language Association of America*, San Diego, December 1994.
- 7.2.30 1994. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Systems Thinking in North American Literary Studies," invited paper, 4th biannual conference, *International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature*, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, August 1994.
- 7.2.29 1994. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Readership Research in Canada: Results and Problems," invited paper, *14th Triennial Congress of the International Comparative Literature Association* (Milan V. Dimić and Steven Tötösy de Zepetnek, org.), University of Alberta, August 1994.
- 7.2.28 1994. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Systemic and Empirical Approach to Literature, the Polysystem Theory, and Translation Theory: The Importance of Methodology," invited paper, *Canadian Association for Translation Studies / Association Canadienne de traductologie*, annual conference, Canadian Learned Societies, University of Calgary, June 1994.
- 7.2.27 1994. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Impact of the Electronic Revolution on Literary Research: A Socio-Semiotic Point of View," invited paper, panel *Canadian Semiotics Association / Association canadienne de sémiotique*, annual conference, Canadian Learned Societies, University of Calgary, June 1994.
- 7.2.26 1994. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Radical Constructivism and the Systemic and Empirical Approach to Literature," invited paper, *International Association for Philosophy and Literature*, University of Alberta, May 1994.
- 7.2.25 1994. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Study of Literature, *consensus ex machina*, and Systems Theory," invited paper, international conference of the *Association for Literary and Linguistic Computing & Association for Computing in the Humanities*, University Paris-Sorbonne Paris IV, April 1994.
- 7.2.24 1993. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "German-Speaking Canadians and Acculturation," invited public lecture, Faculty of Arts, U of Winnipeg, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada, December 1993.
- 7.2.23 1993. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Perceptions of Realism in Döblin's *Berlin Alexanderplatz* and Faßbinder's *Berlin Alexanderplatz*," invited paper, *Parodie, pastiche, mimétisme*, international conference, University of Venezia, October 1993.
- 7.2.22 1993. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Ondaatje's *The English Patient*: Historicity and the Other," invited public lecture, University of Saarland, October 1993.
- 7.2.21 1993. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Erziehung, Erziehungswissenschaft und Multikulturalität in Kanada," invited public lecture, College of Pedagogy Linz, October 1993.
- 7.2.20 1993. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Systemic and Empirical Approach to Literature and Interdisciplinarity: Theory and Application," invited paper, *19th Congress Federation for Modern Languages and Literatures / Fédération Internationale des Langues and Littératures Modernes*, University of Brasília, August 1993.
- 7.2.19 1993. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Systemic Approaches to Literature and Comparative Literature: New Developments," invited paper, international conference of the *International Society for the Systems Sciences*, Ryerson University, June 1993.
- 7.2.18 1993. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Comparative Literature and Its Present Situation," invited public lecture, József Attila University, May 1993.
- 7.2.17 1993. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "What Do We Read?: The 'Canon' and English-Canadian Readership," paper, 14th annual conference, *Canadian Studies*, Cambridge University, March 1993.
- 7.2.16 1992. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "English-Canadian Readers' Perception of 'Truth' and 'Fact' in Fiction: Nineteenth-Century and Contemporary Examples," invited paper, 3rd biannual conference, *International Society for the Empirical Study of Literature*, Memphis State University and Rhodes College, May 1992.
- 7.2.15 1991. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Urban English-Canadian Readership: Selected Results of a Pilot Project," invited public lecture, Institute for Empirical Literature and Media Research, Siegen University, August 1991.
- 7.2.14 1991. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "A feminizmus kezdete a modern magyar irodalomban. Kaffka Margit prózája" ("The Origin of Feminist Writing in Modern Hungarian Literature: The Prose of Margit Kaffka"), invited paper, 4th *World Congress of Hungarian Studies*, József Attila University, August 1991.
- 6.2.13 1991. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Aspects of Literature Drawn from a Readership Survey Conducted in an Urban Environment," invited paper, *Canadian Comparative Literature Association*, annual conference, Canadian Learned Societies, Queen's University, May 1991.
- 7.2.12 1991. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Selected Prose by Margit Kaffka and Dorothy Richardson: An Analysis from a Feminist Point of View," invited paper, panel *Hungarian Studies Association*, annual conference, Canadian Learned Societies, Queen's University, May 1991.
- 7.2.11 1987. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Nineteenth-Century Canadian Prefaces: A Comparative Approach," invited paper, international conference, *The History of the Literary Institution in Canada*, University of Alberta, November 1987.
- 7.2.10 1987. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Canonization and Translation in Canada: A Case Study," invited paper, panel *German-Canadian Studies*, annual conference, Canadian Learned Societies, McMaster University, May 1987.
- 7.2.9 1987. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Towards a History of German-Canadian Literature," invited paper, *Department of Comparative Literature Lecture Series*, University of Alberta, March 1987.
- 7.2.8 1986. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Das Bild der Gesellschaft bei Theodor Fontane und Lajos Tolnai," invited paper, 3rd *World Congress of Hungarian Studies*, University of Vienna, September 1986.
- 7.2.7 1986. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "History as Allusion: Eötvös's *Magyarország 1514-ben*," invited paper, annual conference, *American Hungarian Educators Association*, University of Toronto, May 1986.
- 7.2.6 1986. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Polysystem Theory of Literature and the Translation of German-Canadian Ethnic Literature," invited paper, panel *Canadian Comparative Literature Association*, Canadian Learned Societies annual conference, University of Manitoba, May 1986.
- 7.2.4 1986. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Edmonton's Hungarian Community," invited paper, *Hungarian Studies Association*, annual conference, Canadian Learned Societies annual conference, University of Manitoba, May 1986.
- 7.2.3 1986. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "The Polysystem Theory of Literature and the Question of German-Canadian Ethnic Literature," invited paper, *Department of Comparative Literature Lecture Series*, University of Alberta, January 1986.
- 7.2.2 1985. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Introduction to Modern Hungarian Literature," invited paper, *Department of Comparative Literature Lecture Series*, University of Alberta, October 1985.
- 7.2.1 1985. Tötösy de Zepetnek, Steven. "Fiction and Society in the Novels of Lajos Tolnai," invited paper, *Hungarian Studies Association*, annual conference, Canadian Learned Societies, University of Montréal, June 1985.